

INFLUENCE OF CROSS-FRAME LAYOUTS IN HORIZONTALLY CURVED GIRDER SYSTEMS

Sakthi S.Thangaraj*^a, Lakshmi P. Subramanian ^b

^aGraduate student, Dept. of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India
sakthimithun016@gmail.com

^bAssisant Professor, Dept. of Civil Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India
lakshmipriya@iitm.ac.in

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the influence of various cross-frame arrangements in horizontally curved I-girder systems. Curved girders experience significant torsional moments and additional lateral bending stresses due to curvature. Cross-frames transfer these forces between girders, act as primary load-carrying members, and stabilize curved girder systems. Therefore, the configuration of cross-frames can significantly influence the load paths and the behaviour of the curved girder system. Traditional design practices recommend radial contiguous arrangement of cross-frames between girders, which results in an equal number of braces in all girders, without considering variations in girder stiffness and global load-shifting between girders. This work examines the response of the girders and cross-frames for different staggered cross-frame layouts during the construction stage. A sophisticated finite element model ensures accurate cross-frame responses with eccentric bending effects. Curved I-girder systems with extreme curvatures are studied, and it is observed that the staggered layout shares the load between girders efficiently compared to the conventional radial layout. Also, slightly higher girder rotations are observed in the girders with a staggered layout.

Keywords: Cross-frame analysis, staggered cross-frame layout, horizontal curvature

1 INTRODUCTION

Curved girders experience significant torsion and bending when subjected to gravity loading, unlike straight girders, because of the eccentricity of the chord line joining the supports. Cross-frames reduce the twist and differential deflections between the girders and make them relatively stable. Cross-frames are vital in transferring forces between girders to stabilise them and are primary structural members in curved girder systems. At the same time, cross-frames also provide stability to the flanges and resist the wind loads in straight girder systems. The cross-frame arrangement along the length of the girder significantly influences the behaviour of the system of girders they connect.

The experimental and analytical studies on curved girder systems began in the late 1960s. In 1969, as part of the Consortium of University Research Teams (CURT) project involving several U.S. universities, prototype experiments were conducted to understand curved girder behaviour and develop design methodologies. Subsequently, in 1993, the Curved Steel Bridge Research Project (CSBRP), a large-scale experiment, was conducted in three phases. The first phase focused on understanding the erection sequence of curved girder systems (1), the second phase on the bending strength of curved I-girders in high shear (2) and the third phase on the behaviour of curved girder systems in non-composite and composite stages under dead and live loads (3). Based on the insights gained from the studies on the behaviour of curved girder systems, numerous studies were conducted to understand the significance and behaviour of cross-frames and their arrangement within the system.

A contiguous radial arrangement of cross-frames is recommended by design codes, resulting in larger unbraced lengths in outer girders prone to significant deformations, and smaller unbraced lengths in

inner girders. This contiguous radial arrangement also leads to non-uniform stress distribution in cross-frames. Sharafbayani (4) proposed a skewed cross-frame layout to address this issue, which performed well compared to the contiguous layout. The cross-frames were placed at skewed angles in this layout rather than having a radial orientation. This positioning leads to an optimal unbraced length in all girders within the system. Samatham and Subramanian (5) later studied staggered cross-frame layouts for curved girder systems with tubular cross-frames for a single bridge configuration, similar to those in straight-skew girder systems. This paper focuses on staggered cross-frame layouts in horizontally curved I-girder bridges of different curvatures and single-angle cross-frame chord members. A staggered cross-frame layout provides more cross-frames and smaller unbraced lengths on outer girders, and fewer cross-frames with larger unbraced lengths in the innermost girder. The cross-frames in a staggered layout are radial but not contiguous. These layouts are illustrated in the later sections of the paper. Single-angle members are prone to biaxial bending in addition to normal stresses due to the eccentricity of the loading plane and the principal planes of the angle members.

In this study on different arrangements of cross-frames, the finite element (FE) modelling of the cross-frame is also crucial. The cross-frame assembly consists of the chord members of the cross-frame, the gusset plate and transverse stiffeners or connection plates. The chord members also undergo eccentric bending due to the offset of the loading axis from the cross-sectional principal axes. This offset is due to the presence of gusset plates, eccentric connections, and the unsymmetric nature of cross-sections such as single angles. The typically used beam-element model of the cross-frame does not explicitly model the gusset plate and transverse stiffener in the bracing system, nor does it account for the reduction in the in-plane cross-frame axial stiffness caused by the eccentric bending of chord members. The beam-column behaviour of the cross-frame chord members can significantly decrease its axial stiffness, even up to 100% in some instances (6). Therefore, a sophisticated three-dimensional finite element analysis accounts for eccentric bending in the cross-frame. This paper focuses on the impact of the staggered layouts on the response of curved I-girder systems for two extreme curvatures L_b/R of 0.06 and 0.12 (0.1 radians is the maximum curvature recommended by AASHTO (7)). The studies are limited to a “K-type” configuration with single-angle members.

2 DETAILS OF THE GIRDER AND CROSS-FRAME USED IN CURRENT STUDIES

The girder details considered in this study are similar to those used in the CSBRP Phase III project. Sharafbayani (4) redesigned the girder dimensions for a four-curved girder system that satisfies the AASHTO (8) Strength limit state. *Fig. 1* illustrates the idealised boundary conditions of the girder system. All the girders are restrained from the vertical movements at both supports. Additionally, both supports of the girder G2 are provided with radial and tangential restraints. The girders are not rotationally restrained. The restraints are provided at the web-flange junctions of each girder. The tangential restraint in G2 prevents the rigid body movement of the girder system. *Table 1* lists the section dimensions of the I-girder, the stiffeners (transverse, connection plate) and the radii and lengths of the curved I-girders used in these studies for curvatures of L_b/R of 0.06 and 0.01. Two sets of analyses are carried out with the same section but with different lengths and radii to represent the two curvatures. The connection plate, transverse stiffener and bearing stiffener dimensions for one girder are the same. Full-depth transverse stiffeners are provided at the cross-frame locations in the inner and outer girders.

This study focuses on the construction stage of the non-composite curved girder system, where the girder lacks lateral restraint from the concrete. The cross-frame plays a crucial role in ensuring stability during the non-composite stage. Samatham and Subramanian (5) previously examined the behaviour of the bridge system with $L_b/R = 0.075$, employing circular pipe cross-frame chord members in a “K-type” configuration. The selection of single-angle members is based on their widespread use in cross-frame design due to their ease of fabrication and installation. The schematic diagram of the K cross-frame used is shown in *Fig. 2*, with the dimensions of the components of the

bracing system. Size of the angle member is adopted from the Sharafbayani (4) and designed as per AASHTO (8).

Fig.1. Boundary conditions of the curved girder system, adopted from Sharafbayani (4)

Table 1: Dimensions of the sections in the curved girder system for L_b/R of (a) 0.06 (b) 0.12 radians

Girder	Web $d_w \times t_w$ (mm)	Top flange $b_{ft} \times t_{ft}$ (mm)	Bottom flange $b_{fb} \times t_{fb}$ (mm)	Stiffener $b_s \times t_s$ (mm)	Radius R (m)	Length L (m)
G1	1220 × 10	305 × 25	305 × 25	305 × 25	(a) 57.0 (b) 32.1	(a) 20.5 (b) 23.1
G2	1220 × 10	355 × 25	355 × 25	355 × 25	(a) 59.7 (b) 34.8	(a) 21.5 (b) 25.0
G3	1220 × 10	406 × 25	406 × 25	406 × 25	(a) 62.3 (b) 37.5	(a) 22.4 (b) 27.0
G4	1220 × 10	457 × 25	457 × 35	457 × 25	(a) 65.0 (b) 40.1	(a) 23.4 (b) 28.9

Fig. 2. Section view of the cross frame along with dimensions (in mm) of the components (8)

The contiguous layout and the two staggered layouts examined in this paper are illustrated in Fig. 3. Cross-frames in all three layouts are arranged radially. The contiguous layout maintains an equal number of cross-frames in all girders, spaced equidistantly from each other. The angle subtended between the cross-frames in the contiguous layout remains the same. In the staggered and reverse-staggered layouts, the subtended angle between the cross-frames and the number of cross-frames change in each girder. Cross-frames in the staggered layout are uniformly distributed within the girder. In the contiguous layout, all the girders have an L_b/R of 0.06 and 0.12 radians, whereas in the staggered layout, girders with six cross-frames have an L_b/R of 0.07 and 0.14 radians. The girders with eight cross-frames have an L_b/R of 0.05 and 0.1 radians. Although the AASHTO (7)

Specifications restrict designers to a maximum L_b/R of 0.1 radians; in this study, we use a maximum curvature of 0.14 radians to investigate the behaviour of curved girders with staggered layouts in tight curvatures. In the staggered layout, the inner girder has a higher L_b/R ratio while in the reverse-staggered layout, the outer girder has a larger L_b/R ratio.

Fig. 3. Different cross-frame layouts studied adapted from Samatham and Subramanian (5)

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The curved girder systems in this paper are modelled in ABAQUS (9). Curved I-girders, transverse stiffeners, gusset plates, and cross-frame chord members are the key components of these FE models. S4R (4-noded Reduced Integration) and S3R (3-noded Reduced Integration) type shell elements are used in modelling the bridge system components. The different components are connected in one of two ways: by coincidental nodes and by using tie connections to connect the components.

The “coincidental node” connects two components with the same mesh density by merging their common nodes. This method is applicable only if the two components lie on the same plane and the centroidal planes of the two components do not have any physical gap between them in the plane of connection. The I-girder flanges, web, and connection plates are connected at coincident nodes.

However, components with different mesh densities, and centroidal planes lying on different planes are connected using various interactions available in ABAQUS (9). The tie constraint adopted by Park et al. (10) ensures that the rotations and displacements of the primary node (with active degrees of freedom) are rigidly connected to the corresponding degrees of freedom of the secondary node (which is to be connected to the primary node). Extensive validation studies have been conducted to verify the behaviour of the tie constraint and to compare the tie interaction results with analytical and experimental results.

Since the girder system is analysed only in the critical non-composite construction stage, linear elastic analysis is carried out, and material non-linearity is not included in the analyses. The Young’s modulus of elasticity E is 200 GPa, and the Poisson’s ratio, ν is 0.3. Geometric non-linear analyses using the Newton-Raphson technique are carried out to accurately capture the stresses and displacements due to curvature. Mesh convergence studies indicate that a girder mesh size of 40mm and cross-frame mesh size of 15mm is optimum, and five to ten increments are sufficient to capture the second-order effects. Hence, loads are applied in ten load increments in this study. The self-weight of the girder and the cross-frame components are applied as gravity load, and the dead load of the wet

concrete is applied on the curved I-girders as a pressure load on their top flanges. The pressure load on each girder is calculated from its tributary area, as explained by Jung (3). In extreme girders, the overhang of the slab (0.914m) is converted to torque by applying a couple of distributed lateral forces - one on the top flange and the other 0.914m (3ft) below the top flange, as depicted in *Fig. 4*. The weight of the concrete and the overhang load of the concrete is maintained same in the different curvature studies discussed in this paper.

Fig. 4. Perspective view of the FE model of the curved girder system (without self-weight of the system)

Extensive validation studies confirm the correctness of the tie interaction, as well as the cross-frame and curved girder system behaviour. The tie interaction within the cross-frame is validated with a small-scale experimental test on the eccentric bending of the angle member conducted by Wang (6). The behaviour of a single K-type cross-frame is validated through an in-plane stiffness experimental test performed by Battistini (11). Further, the curved girder system model is validated against the erection studies conducted by Linzell (1) as a part of the CSBRP Phase I project. The model demonstrates a favourable agreement with both experimental and analytical results in all validation test simulations.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The girder and cross-frame response of the curved girder system for the curvatures discussed in Section 2 is assessed in this section. The studies focus on specific girder responses - web rotation, vertical displacement, and flange normal stresses during construction. These responses can affect the overall stability and fit-up of the girder.

Web rotation is a critical parameter in construction, and excessive rotation can lead to fit-up issues, especially at splice locations. In curved girders, web rotation serves as an indicator of the girder's torsion and instability levels. Design codes do not specify a serviceability limit for web rotation; a common practice in design is to adhere to a maximum web rotation of 1.5 degrees as a rule of thumb (12). However, this limit of web rotation is not considered in this study. *Fig. 5* and *Fig. 6* show the web rotations for the extreme girders of the girder systems with L_b/R of 0.06 and 0.12. Interestingly, the maximum web rotations in staggered layouts are less than those in the contiguous layout in the innermost girder G1. Despite the outermost girder G4 having more cross-frames in both staggered layouts than in the contiguous layout, the web rotation is higher in the staggered layouts.

Fig. 7 shows the vertical displacements of the girders with L_b/R of 0.06 and 0.12 radians. There is no significant difference in the vertical displacement of the girder for the different cross-frame layouts. There is a 3% increase in the deflection in staggered layouts compared to the contiguous layout in G1 and an increase of 3.5% in G4 for the curvature of 0.06 radian. A slight decrease in the in-plane

deflection is observed in the intermediate girders of both staggered layouts compared to the contiguous radial layout. These observations are true for curved girder systems, irrespective of curvature.

Fig. 5. Web rotation of fascia girders for different cross-frame layouts with L_b/R of 0.06 radians

Fig. 6. Web rotation of fascia girders for different cross-frame layouts with L_b/R of 0.12 radians

Fig. 7. Maximum in-plane deflection of the fascia girders with L_b/R of (a) 0.06 (b) 0.12 radians

The bottom flange exterior tip normal stress is the maximum normal stress at the bottom flange as the flange undergoes lateral bending along with in-plane bending. This normal stress depends directly on the number of cross-frames between the girders, as the cross-frame acts as a lateral support to the flanges. The normal stresses at the bottom flange exterior tips are shown in *Fig. 8* and *Fig. 9* for the extreme girders with L_b/R of 0.06 and 0.12 radians. In the staggered layout, the flange normal stress in G1 is greater than in other layouts because of the difference in the number of cross-frames between the G1-G2 junction. Similarly, in the G4 girder, the normal stress is greater for the reverse-staggered layout due to the same reason. Similar to other responses, the same trend of bending stress is observed irrespective of the girder curvature.

Fig. 8. Bottom flange exterior tip normal stresses in fascia girders for different cross-frame layouts with L_b/R of 0.06

Fig. 9. Bottom flange exterior tip normal stresses in fascia girders for different cross-frame layouts with L_b/R of 0.12

The angle members in the cross-frames undergo axial deformation and biaxial bending since forces from the girders are not applied along the principal planes of the angle members. In addition to the eccentricity of force from the gusset plate to the angle member, there is an additional eccentricity in load transfer from the transverse stiffener to the gusset plate. This eccentricity also causes bending, but its significance depends on the relative thickness of the stiffener and the gusset plate. Additionally, the rigid connections between the girders and the cross-frames allow moment transfer between them. Furthermore, angle members experience shear lag effects. The angle members behave like beam-columns, and assuming the chord members to be pinned at their ends is unrealistic.

The distribution of the resultant normal stress in the connected leg of the top chord angle member at five discrete locations along its length is shown in Fig. 10. Fig. 11 shows the distribution of the resultant normal stress at the free end of the leg connected to the gusset plate for all the chords in the cross-frame. The stress distributions in the cross-frame at position 3R from the G3-G4 junction in the contiguous layout are shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. The variation in normal stress along the length of the chord is observed here, unlike in the line element model where there is a constant stress because of pin-jointed chords. The bottom centre plate (plate 3 defined in Fig. 2) transfers both moment and shear, as shown in Fig. 11, whereas in the line element model, the elements intersect to form rigid joints, and the plate is not explicitly modelled.

Fig. 10. Normal stress distribution of the top chord angle connected leg at five locations along the chord

Fig. 11. Normal stress distribution of the top chord angle connected leg at free end along the chord

The top chord experiences larger stresses at mid-span than the other chords at all cross-frame positions, except at the 4L/4R location. Hence, the stress in the top chord can be compared for the

different cross-frame layouts. Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 compare the mid-span normal stresses in the top chords for cross-frames between G1-G2 and G3-G4 of different layouts at L_b/R values of 0.06 and 0.12 radians. An increase in cross-frame normal stress is observed in girders with fewer cross-frames, while a decrease is seen in the girders with greater number of cross-frames than in the conventional layout. The difference in stress distribution occurs due to the load-sharing by cross-frames. A similar trend of stress distribution is observed in cross-frames, irrespective of the curvature of the girders.

Fig. 12. Top chord mid-span normal stress at (a) G1-G2 (b) G3-G4 junction for L_b/R of 0.06

Fig. 13. Top chord mid-span normal stress at (a) G1-G2 (b) G3-G4 junction for L_b/R of 0.12

5 CONCLUSIONS

A single-span curved I-girder system with a staggered and reverse-staggered radial layout is compared to a radial contiguous layout. The following conclusions are drawn regarding the behaviour of both layouts in the curved girder system:

1. The web rotations in the critical girder G4 increase for both staggered layouts. However, the increase in web rotation is minimal in the staggered layout compared to the reverse-staggered layout. In the extreme curvature of $L_b/R = 0.12$, the web rotation increase is approximately 10% for the staggered layout.
2. There is no significant change in vertical displacement for different cross-frame layouts studied.

3. The staggered layout results in smaller flange bending stresses in the critical girder G4 and greater stresses in girder G1, while the reverse-staggered layout results in higher flange bending stresses in the critical girder G4 and lower stresses in girder G1 compared to the contiguous layout.
4. In the staggered layout, cross-frame stresses increase in the inner girder bay, which experiences less stress, and decreases in the outer girder bay, which experiences more stress. This indicates more efficient utilization of cross-frames in the inner bay compared to the outer bay. The reverse-staggered layout performs poorly, increasing stress in the outer junction where cross-frames already experience greater stress levels.

In summary, this paper examines the response of the curved girder system during construction for different cross-frame layouts. The girder system, with extreme curvatures, is analysed using linear elastic analyses with second-order effects. The staggered layouts perform well by reducing stresses in the critical girder and cross-frames compared to the conventional radial layout. Although a slight increase in girder displacement response is noted, it is not a cause for significant concern. Consequently, the staggered layout might be considered an alternative in curved girder systems, with a broad range of parametric studies on a fully composite bridge warranted.

REFERENCES

1. Linzell Daniel, G. *Studies of a full-scale horizontally curved steel I-girder bridge system under self-weight*. Ph.D. Dissertation, School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA, 1999.
2. Zureick, A. et al. Curved steel girders: Experimental and analytical studies. A: *Engineering Structures*. 2000, Vol. 22, p. 180-190.
3. Jung, S.-K. *Inelastic strength behavior of horizontally curved composite I-girder bridge structural systems*. Ph.D. Dissertation, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, 2006.
4. Sharafbayani, M. *Evaluation of bracing systems in horizontally curved I-girder bridges*. PhD Dissertation, Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Pennsylvania State University, 2012.
5. Samatham, N. and Subramanian, L.P. *The influence of staggered cross frame layout on the behavior of horizontally curved steel I-girder bridges* *Proceedings of the Annual Stability Conference, Structural Stability Research Council, SSRC* . San Antonio, Texas: 2024(To appear).
6. Wang Weihua. *A study of stiffness of steel bridge cross frames*. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Texas, Austin, 2013.
7. AASHTO. *LRFD bridge design specifications*. 9th Edition Washington D.C.: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials National Steel Bridge Alliance AASHTO/NSBA Steel Bridge Collaboration, 2020.
8. AASHTO. *LRFD bridge design specifications*. 6th Edition. Washington D.C.: American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials, 2012.
9. Simulia. ABAQUS/Standard Version 6.19. A: *Simulia, Inc., Providence, RI*. Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp, 2023, p. 1-1592.
10. Park, S. et al. *Improved cross-frame analysis and design : wide-flange T-shape sections*. A: . National Cooperative Highway Research Program, Project 12-113: 2023. ISBN 9780309698689.
11. Battistini, A.D. *Stiffness and fatigue behavior of cross frames for steel bridge applications*. Ph.D. Dissertation, The University of Texas, Austin, 2014.
12. Farris, J.F. *Behavior of horizontally curved steel I-Girders during construction*. Master Thesis, The University of Texas, Austin, 2008.